

Recycling Large-Scale 3D Printed Polymer Composite Precast Concrete Forms

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ABSTRACT

Large-scale thermoplastic extrusion-based 3D printing, also referred to as additive manufacturing (AM), has shown promise for a multitude of applications in civil infrastructure. Advancements in this technology have led to increased usage and a subsequent increase in generated waste. Recently, the opportunity to recycle this material has contributed to lessening this waste. Presented in this work are established baseline thermo-mechanical and physical properties of carbon fiber – acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (CF-ABS) and wood flour – amorphous poly lactic acid (WF-aPLA). Additionally, this work is to be used in comparison with subsequent recycling cycles in evaluation of the mechanical recycling process for large-scale 3D printed CF-ABS and WF-aPLA with intended applications as formwork for precast concrete.

KEYWORDS

Large-scale 3D printing; Recyclability; Thermoplastic Composites; Precast Concrete Formwork; Additive Manufacturing

INTRODUCTION

Large-scale, thermoplastic composite, extrusion-based 3D printing or AM has been applied in infrastructure applications. Recent construction applications that have been demonstrated are:

- Outlet diffuser for highway culvert rehabilitation (Bhandari et al., 2021);
- Precast concrete formwork for a parking garage structure (Bhandari et al., 2022);
- BioHome3D, which is a 56 m² modular house manufactured using a bio-polymer filled with wood fiber, which is recyclable (Ferrini-Mundi and Varahramyan, 2023).

One significant use of large-scale 3D printing has been to make forms for precast concrete parts. The use of large-scale 3D printing as a method of formwork manufacturing provides geometric freedom for design while utilizing traditional concrete casting techniques. Alongside this, the use of large-scale 3D printing offers the added benefit of being an automated manufacturing process, which in turn reduces labor costs. Despite these advantages, printing large-scale parts produces tonnes of waste annually (Mikula et al., 2020). Landfill waste is a large contributor to global pollution and climate change, since they release large amounts of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere (Lou et. al., 2009). The introduction of additional solid waste streams, such as 3D printed waste material, not only will contribute to global pollution but also will contribute to the increased need for landfills. The 3D printed formworks discarded after casting concrete will perpetuate the amount of pollution entering the atmosphere. Recycling 3D printed formworks manufactured using thermoplastic composite materials can help mitigate the problem and needs to be further investigated for technical and economic viability.

There are three commonly used methods for the recycling of thermoplastic composite materials: chemical, mechanical, and thermal recycling. Both chemical and thermal recycling are methods of fiber reinforcement recovery. Therefore, the matrix material is mostly wasted and does not contribute to the circular economy of the composite. Mechanical recycling is a method that recycles both the composite matrix and fiber reinforcements.

Table 1 provides a summary of the advantages and disadvantages of the three recycling techniques (Baek et al., 2018; Pietroluongo et al., 2020).

Table 1: Summary of recycling techniques

Recycling Technique	Benefits of Technique	Disadvantages of Technique
Chemical Recycling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimal damage to fibers • Increased energy efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adverse environmental impact from chemical usage • Mostly recycles fibers and not matrix material
Mechanical Recycling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Most simplistic process • Recycles entire composite (matrix and fibers) • Possible reductions in energy consumption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decreases fiber quality • Smaller grinding screens increase energy consumption
Thermal Recycling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No effect on fiber length • Possibility for shorter recycling period 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased energy consumption • Elevated temperatures are detrimental to the fibers • Only recycles fibers and not matrix material

Several studies have been conducted with the goal of addressing the viability of recycling 3D printed thermoplastic composite materials. However, there are conflicting findings from these studies. A study by Zhao et al. found recycling to be both economically and environmentally viable (Zhao et al., 2018). However, Zhao et al. concluded that the material could only undergo two recycling cycles, if the material is to retain its rheological properties (Zhao et al., 2018). Additionally, a study by Anderson found that there are significant differences in the mechanical properties of virgin material compared to the mechanical properties of recycled material and concluded that the recycling process is environmentally viable (Anderson, 2017). A study conducted by Copenhaver et al. found that the recycled material had little to no degradation in the observed material properties, in addition to concluding that recycling the material significantly reduced the material’s embodied energy (Copenhaver et al., 2023).

This research aims to address uncertainty in the mechanical recycling process through the use of five recycling cycles and a life cycle analysis (LCA), to produce recommendations on economic and environmental viability of the recycling process for large-scale 3D printed CF-ABS and WF-aPLA polymer composites for precast concrete formwork. Note that during each cycle, before the formworks are recycled, concrete is cast in the formwork.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The formwork sets were manufactured using the Ingersoll MasterPrint large-scale 3D printer (Ingersoll Machine Tools, Inc., Rockford, IL, USA). This machine utilized a single screw extrusion head, with a screw diameter of 30 mm and a nozzle diameter of 12.7 mm. Figure 1 shows this 3D printer manufacturing precast concrete forms, at the Advanced Structures and Composites Center (ASCC), at the University of Maine.

Figure 1: Ingersoll MasterPrint large-scale 3D printer extrusion head.

Two polymer composite materials, one synthetic and one bio-based, were selected for the manufacturing process. A total of ten sets of forms were manufactured, five sets of synthetic material (CF-ABS) forms and five sets of bio-based material (WF-aPLA) forms. Table 2 summarizes the material properties of the compounded material, provided by the material compounders.

Table 2: Summary of compounded material thermo-mechanical properties

Material	Material Compounder	Reinforcement (% by weight)	Tensile Strength at Break (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (MPa)	Glass Transition Temperature (°C)
CF-ABS	TECHMER- Polymer Modifiers	20	110	N/A	N/A
WF-aPLA	JABIL	20	N/A	4900	61.2

The formwork had a length of 61 cm (24 in), a width of 31 cm (12 in), and a height of 61 cm (24 in). The formwork thickness was 3.8 cm (1.5 in), which is the equivalent of two printed bead widths. Drawings of the formwork with dimensions are shown in Figure 2. The parameters for the 3D printing are listed in Table 3.

Table 3: Printing parameters by feedstock materials

Printing Parameter	CF-ABS	WF-aPLA
Bead width	20 mm (0.80 in)	20 mm (0.80 in)
Bead thickness	5 mm (0.20 in)	5 mm (0.20 in)
Extrusion rate	~50 kg/hr (~108 lbs/hr)	~37 kg/hr (~82 lbs/hr)
Extrusion temperature	247°C	203°C

Figure 2: Drawings of the 3D printed formwork.

Post processing methods were also used on the formwork sets. The forms were cut at the corners, into four pieces. Each set of forms had a total of 24, 9.5 mm (0.375 in) holes, drilled into them (six holes per panel). The interior faces of the formwork sets were machined to ensure a smooth/even surface for casting. Figure 3 shows sets of both the CF-ABS and the WF-aPLA formwork pieces. In addition to the 3D printed forms, hexagons were manufactured under the same conditions to provide coupons samples for material characterization.

Figure 3: 3D printed formwork pieces.

Characterization Methods

The baseline material properties were determined using tensile tests, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), microscopy, size exclusion chromatography (SEC), and a rheology study Table 4 presents a summary of material properties obtained and the methods used to obtain them. Note that the 1-direction corresponds to the direction of deposition of the bead, the 2-direction is transverse to the direction of deposition in the plane of the bead, and the 3-direction is through the thickness of the layer.

Table 4: Experimentally Characterized Properties of Polymer Composites and Test Methods

Polymer Composite Material	Measured Property	Test Method
CF-ABS	Tensile Strength	ASTM D3039
	Tensile Modulus	
	Poisson's Ratio	
	Glass Transition Temperature	ASTM E1356-08
	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	ASTM E831-19
	Material Impurities	Wang et al., 2019
	Fiber Length	Bhandari et al., 2019
	Complex Modulus	Walker et al., 2022
	Complex Viscosity	
	Viscosity	
Molecular Weight	Khoda et al., 2023	
WF-aPLA	Tensile Strength	ASTM D3039
	Tensile Modulus	
	Poisson's Ratio	
	Glass Transition Temperature	ASTM E1356-08
	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	ASTM E831-19
	Material Impurities	Wang et al., 2019
	Fiber Length	Bhandari et al., 2019
	Complex Modulus	Walker et al., 2022
	Complex Viscosity	
	Viscosity	
Molecular Weight	Khoda et al., 2023	

Thermal Tests

The DSC tests were conducted in accordance with ASTM E1356-08 standard test method (ASTM, 2014), with a testing procedure similar to that of Colón Quintana et al. (2022). Samples of approximately 5 mg were tested using a TA Instruments DSC2500 (TA Instruments, New Castel, DE, USA). All samples were tested in TA's Tzero Aluminum pans. Samples were first equilibrated at 20°C. The samples were then heated from 20°C to 200°C at a rate of 10°C/min. The temperature was held at 200°C for one minute, to ensure the DSC achieved equilibrium. Samples were then cooled to 20°C, at a rate of 10°C/min. Samples were then exposed to an isothermal environment, for one minute. Following this, samples were heated to 200°C at a rate of 10°C/min. Three samples of each 3D printed material were tested to ensure repeatability of results. The glass transition temperature was determined using an average of the midpoint temperatures, as defined in ASTM E1356-08, from the heat flow curve generated by the second heating ramp.

The method used to perform the TGA tests was based on the method used by Wang et al. Adjustments were made to account for differences in polymer matrix material. All TGA tests were conducted on a TA Instruments Q500 (TA Instruments, New Castel, DE, USA). The tests were conducted with a ramp procedure of 10°C/min to 700°C, in a nitrogen atmosphere. The nitrogen atmosphere was selected to prevent oxidization of the samples and had a flow rate of 50mL/min. Tests were conducted on samples collected before and after the forms were pressure washed.

In addition, a rheology study was conducted. Rheologic behaviors were measured using a TA Instruments Discovery HR-3 hybrid rheometer. Oscillatory and shear tests were conducted on 8 mm, stainless steel, parallel plates with a 1 mm gap. Samples were molded at extrusion temperature, with approximately 14 MPa of pressure. Prior to molding, the CF-ABS material and the WF-aPLA material was dried at 80 °C and 40 °C for four hours, respectively. The oscillatory and shear test methods were based on that of the method used by Walker et al., with modifications to the testing parameters. Oscillatory and shear testing parameters can be found in Table 5 and Table 6, respectively.

Table 5: Rheometer Oscillatory Testing Parameters

Test Type	Material	Temperature (°C)	Soak Time (sec)	Oscillating Angular Frequency (rad/sec)	Strain (%)	Sampling Rate (points/decade)
Amplitude Sweep	CF-ABS	247	180	10.0	0.01 - 100	5
	WF-aPLA	203	180	10.0	0.01 - 100	5
Frequency Sweep	CF-ABS	247	180	100 – 0.1	0.5	5
	WF-aPLA	203	180	100 – 0.1	0.05	5

Table 6: Rheometer Shear Testing Parameters

Test Type	Material	Temperature (°C)	Soak Time (sec)	Shear Rate (1/sec)	Sampling Rate (points/decade)
Flow Sweep	CF-ABS	247	180	1.0 – 100	5
	WF-aPLA	203	180	1.0 – 100	5

Mechanical Tests

The tensile tests were conducted in accordance with a modified ASTM D3039-17 standard test method. A deviation from the standard on the specimen dimensions was adopted to capture the unit cell of the of the 3D printed material based on the bead size. The tensile specimens had a width of 40 mm, thickness of 10 mm, and a length of 250 mm. A constant head-speed test was used, with a displacement rate of 2 mm/min. The tensile tests were conducted using a 100 kN (22 kip) Instron 2527-111 series load cell (Instron Corporation, Norwood, MA, USA). GOM ARAMIS digital image correlation (DIC) was the selected method for determining the strain field over a 50 mm gauge region. Two, 12 MP Basler cameras were used for image capture. A stochastic, black and white, speckle pattern was used in the gauge region. A combination of Streampix, LabVIEW, and GOM Correlate 2019 software packages were used to trigger and capture images during the tensile tests.

Physical Property Testing

A matrix dissolution was performed to isolate fibers from the composite matrix. A method similar to the one used by Bhandari et al. (2019), was used to perform the dissolution. Chloroform (CHCl₃) was used as the solvent. WF-aPLA and CF-ABS samples of approximately 0.5 g were placed into a chloroform bath and then onto a stirring plate. The dissolution process was allowed to occur over a two-day period at ambient temperature. The fibers were then filtered and rinsed with dichloromethane (CH₂Cl₂).

Microscopy using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) and ImageJ software, was used to analyze the baseline fiber lengths. Images of the isolated fibers were taken using a Hitachi 3000 SEM. All images were taken at x250 magnification. All fibers, whose full length were in the image window were measured.

SEC, also known as gel permeation chromatography (GPC) was conducted using an Agilent 1260 Infinity Size Exclusion Chromograph, using a method similar to the one used by Khoda et. al. (2023). Samples were approximately 5 mg, in weight. Prior to testing samples were placed into a high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) grade tetrahydrofuran solvent. Testing was performed

using a concentration between 1 mg/mL and 3 mg/mL of polymer in solvent. Samples were passed through a 0.2 μm PTFE syringe filter prior to injection and were analyzed with an eluent of tetrahydrofuran at a 1 mL/min flowrate. These tests were conducted at 35°C.

Formwork Preparation

All sets of formwork were assembled using hex-coil bolts. Following assembly and prior to casting, Sakrete Form Release Oil was applied to the walls of the forms, using a brush.

Concrete Casting

Expanded polystyrene blocks (EPS) of dimensions 51 cm x 20 cm x 61 cm (20 in x 8 in x 24 in) were covered in plastic and placed into the center of the assembled formwork. Covering the EPS blocks in plastic prevented the concrete from adhering to the blocks. The EPS blocks were used as voids, to minimize the amount of concrete cast. Concrete was prepared in accordance with ASTM C192, Standard Practice for Making and Curing Concrete Test Specimens in the Laboratory (ASTM, 2020). Concrete was then cast around the covered EPS voids. The concrete was allowed to cure for 24 hours. Following the cure time, the forms were stripped, and concrete was disposed of. The formwork pieces were then washed using a pressure washer.

DISCUSSION RESULTS

The initial tests resulted in an established baseline for both the CF-ABS and WF-aPLA materials. These baseline values will be used comparatively with future recycled material, to establish any degradations/changes in material properties.

Thermal Test Results

The DSC tests were used to establish the glass transition temperature of the formwork material. The heat flow curves, produced by the second heating ramp, are shown in Figure 4. Table 7 summarizes the glass transition temperatures for both materials.

Figure 4: Normalized heat flow curve of (a) CF-ABS, (b) WF-aPLA

Table 7: Glass transition temperature for baseline 3D printed composite material

Composite Material	Sample Name	Glass Transition Temperature (°C)	Mean Glass Transition Temperature (°C)
CF-ABS	CF-1	102.5	102
	CF-2	101.1	
	CF-3	101.8	
WF-aPLA	WF-1	54.4	54.4
	WF-2	54.3	
	WF-3	54.4	

The TGA tests were used to determine the impurities present in the material after the forms had been used to cast concrete. Through a comparison of pre-wash and post-wash samples it was possible to

determine the effectiveness of the washing procedure. Table 8 is a summary of the TGA data for both the pre-wash and post-wash samples, including the total average impurities found in the samples after washing. The effectiveness of washing the forms after concrete casting is assessed by the percentage of residuals measured from TGA tests, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Residual percentage mass from TGA

Material	Sample Name	Pre-Wash (%)	Post-Wash (%)	Mean Residuals Pre-Wash (%)	Mean Residuals Post-Wash (%)
CF-ABS	CF-1	0.00	0.24	0.51	0.08
	CF-2	0.77	0.00		
	CF-3	0.75	0.00		
WF-aPLA	WF-1	5.3	0.40	2.60	0.29
	WF-2	1.4	0.47		
	WF-3	1.1	0.0		

Figure 5 is a graphical representation of the TGA data for pre-wash and post-wash samples for CF-ABS and WF-aPLA.

Figure 5a: Pre- and post-wash comparison of CF-ABS thermal gravimetry

Figure 5b: Pre- and post-wash comparison of WF-aPLA thermal gravimetry

The rheology study was used to determine both the complex viscosities and viscosities of the materials. The complex viscosity of the materials as a function of angular frequency is shown in Figure 6a and the viscosity of the materials as a function of shear rate is shown in Figure 6b. Note that the data presented in Figure 6b is truncated. Data truncation was necessary due to rotational rheometer limitations, where material slippage occurs at high shear rates.

Figure 6a: Complex viscosity as a function of angular frequency

Figure 6b: Viscosity as a function of shear rate

The apparent shear rate of the material at the nozzle can be approximated using Equation 1 (Agassant et. al., 2017).

$$\dot{\gamma} = \frac{4Q}{\pi r^3} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where Q is the volumetric flow rate and r is the radius of the nozzle. The shear rate at the nozzle of the CF-ABS and WF-aPLA, according to Equation 1, is approximately 11.2 Pa.s and 3.69 Pa.s, respectively.

Mechanical Test Results

The baseline tensile properties of both the CF-ABS and WF-aPLA were determined and are represented in Table 9. The stress-strain curves shown in Figure 7 are representative of the sample tensile data for both materials.

Table 9: Baseline tensile properties

Material	Direction	Number of Samples	Average Tensile Modulus (MPa) (Coefficient of Variation)	Average Tensile Strength (MPa) (Coefficient of Variation)	Poisson's Ratio (Coefficient of Variation)
CF-ABS	1-Direction	5	4892 (11%)	40.46 (10%)	0.36 (4.0%)
	3-Direction	4	2454 (0.46%)	19.71 (11%)	0.18 (22%)
WF-aPLA	1-Direction	5	4292 (1.2%)	39.64 (5.2%)	0.35 (0.83%)
	3-Direction	5	3725 (5.7%)	23.67 (13%)	0.30 (5.5%)

Figure 7a: Tensile stress vs. axial strain for CF-ABS in 1-direction.

Figure 7b: Tensile stress vs. axial strain for CF-ABS in 3-direction.

Figure 7c: Tensile stress vs. axial strain for WF-aPLA samples in 1-direction.

Figure 7d: Tensile stress vs. axial strain for WF-aPLA samples in 3-direction.

Physical Test Results

A matrix dissolution was used to isolate the reinforcing fibers from the matrices. Microscopy using SEM and ImageJ was used to determine the baseline fiber lengths for both the wood flour fibers and the carbon fibers. Figure 8 is representative of the distribution of the fiber lengths and shows that both the carbon fibers and the wood flour fibers have a positive skew.

Figure 8: Distribution of (a) wood flour fiber lengths and (b) carbon fiber lengths

GPC was used to quantify the molecular weight of the compounded material and the material post-baseline print.

Table 10: Feedstock pellet material molecular weight from GPC

Composite Material	Polymer	Mean Molecular Weight (M_n)	Polydispersity (PD)
CF-ABS	ABS	90261	1.88
WF-aPLA	aPLA	45007	3.32

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Both the 3D printing and post-3D printing processes were successful in manufacturing sets of formwork. Assembly of the machined parts, for concrete casting, was simple and non-labor intensive. The concrete parts cast resulted in smooth surface finishes. Following the casting of the concrete, the forms were stripped with ease. However, it was observed that some water absorption may have occurred in the WF-aPLA forms. Water absorption will be monitored and measured in subsequent cycles.

Thermal Properties

The post-casting washing procedure, of the formwork, was proven to be effective. The introduced impurities were less than 0.5% for both the CF-ABS and WF-aPLA forms. The pre- and post-wash comparisons show an 84% reduction in impurities for the CF-ABS forms and an 83% reduction in material impurities for the WF-aPLA forms.

The established baseline value for the glass transition temperature (T_g) of WF-aPLA was comparable to the value provided by the material compounder. The baseline value being 11% lower than the reported value by the compounder. The T_g for the CF-ABS was not available through the material compounder. However, the established baseline value, of approximately 102 °C, is comparable to the values reported in literature. Yu et. al. (2020) found the T_g of CF-ABS to be approximately 100 °C.

The oscillatory rheometer tests showed that at low frequencies the CF-ABS and the WF-aPLA have similar complex viscosities. As angular frequency increases, the complex viscosities of the CF-ABS and the WF-aPLA diverge. With increasing angular frequency, the complex viscosity of the CF-ABS becomes increasingly greater than that of the WF-aPLA. With both the CF-ABS and the WF-aPLA having complex viscosities that decrease with angular frequency.

The shear rheometer tests show that for the tested shear rate range, the CF-ABS has a greater viscosity than that of the WF-aPLA. Shear thinning of the materials is visible in Figure 6b, by the decreasing

material viscosity with the increasing shear rate (Vlachopoulos et. al., 2016). Therefore, it is possible to classify both the CF-ABS and the WF-aPLA as non-Newtonian fluids.

Mechanical Properties

The measured baseline tensile properties showed, on average, both the CF-ABS and WF-aPLA materials were stronger in the 1-direction, than the 3-direction. The results also showed that the 1-direction CF-ABS samples were 2.5% stronger than the 1-direction WF-aPLA samples. However, in the 3-direction the WF-aPLA samples were 18% stronger than the CF-ABS samples. Similar trends were observed in the tensile moduli of the samples. In the 1-direction the CF-ABS samples had a greater modulus and in the 3-direction the WF-aPLA samples had a greater modulus. The material is expected to have higher strength and modulus in the 1-direction compared to the strength in the 3-direction, due to the preferential alignment of fibers in the 1-direction, as well as the existence of “welding lines” formed by the incomplete polymer diffusion among deposited layers.

In the 1-direction the CF-ABS samples had a modulus 12% greater than that of the WF-aPLA samples. While the 3-direction showed that the WF-aPLA samples had a modulus that was 42% greater than that of the CF-ABS samples.

Note that the tensile strength of the CF-ABS in the 1- and 3-directions are approximately 70% and 80% less than the tensile strength value reported by the material compounder, respectively. This reduction in strength can be attributed to the sample manufacturing method selected. The material compounder utilized an injection molding (IM), rather than large-scale 3D printing. Samples manufactured with IM have little to no void content (Selva Priya et. al, 2019). Additionally, IM samples have a singular layer structure, meaning bead adhesion does not contribute/alter the sample strength.

Physical Properties

The baseline fiber length for the carbon fibers had an average of approximately 82 μm , with a lower quartile, median, and upper quartile of approximately 42 μm , 66 μm , and 100 μm , respectively. These values are comparative to those found in literature. Karsli et al. (2012) found the maximum number of fibers were in a range of 51 μm – 100 μm . The baseline fiber length for the wood flour had an average length of approximately 97 μm , with a lower quartile, median, and upper quartile of 62 μm , 89 μm , and 116 μm , respectively. For comparison, Madyan et al. (2020) found that the average length of wood flour fibers was approximately $164 \pm 63 \mu\text{m}$.

The GPC test results show that the ABS has a higher molecular weight than the aPLA. The results also show that the MW distribution of the aPLA polymer chains is approximately 77% greater than that of the MW distribution of the ABS polymer chains.

FUTURE WORK

In the subsequent recycling cycles, a material loss is anticipated during the shredding process. Knowing this anticipated loss, each subsequent recycled 3D print is planned to have fewer forms manufactured than the number of forms in the previous cycle. The effects of any possible material degradation on thermal, mechanical, and physical properties will be established with reference to the reported baseline properties.

CONCLUSIONS

Two sets of 3D printed forms were successfully manufactured on the large-scale. The machining methods used on the faces of the formwork created a smooth surface finish on the cast concrete parts. The machined surfaces and chosen formwork-release agent allowed the forms to be stripped easily from the cast concrete part. The chosen washing methods of the composite formwork, post-casting, proved to be an effective method of minimizing the number of impurities introduced to the formwork. The baseline values, to be used in comparison with future recycled 3D printed forms, were measured and recorded. These values were comparable to those found in the literature, internal and those made available by the material compounders. Additionally, the baseline characterization showed that the CF-ABS has a greater viscosity and is less sensitive to temperature than the WF-aPLA. The results also showed that the CF-ABS has a greater tensile strength than the WF-aPLA.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.